

THE EFFECT OF SERVICE QUALITY AND CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

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Abstract

The key to the success of an organization is customer satisfaction by improving the service quality provided by drivers because a high level of customer satisfaction will encourage users to continue using Grab and make it a viable alternative to other online transportation options. As well as having customers will improve their experience by fostering strong and close relationships with them and improving the services they need. So, to increase customer satisfaction with Grab transportation. So as to benefit the Company. This study aims to determine customer satisfaction and service quality as well as the experience of Grab transportation users. The sampling technique is a total sampling of 750 respondents. Data collection was carried out through literature studies and the dissemination of questionnaires. This study uses the Multi Attribute Model (MAM) model to determine the Effect of Service Quality and Customer Experience on Customer Satisfaction. The number of students in this study at the Faculty of Economics Class of 2016, Medan State University is 750 people. So far, the information conveyed by customers to researchers so that communication is well established.

Keywords: Effect of Service Quality, Customer Experience, Customer Satisfaction

1. INTRODUCTION

The current state of marketing in Indonesia is one of the growth and development that is shifting from traditional marketing to modern marketing. The large number of competitors, increasingly sophisticated technology, and the development of marketing education, all encourage businesses to innovate and develop strategies to meet customer expectations. The business world is encouraged to know market changes and be able to come up with innovative ideas so that the products offered can attract the attention of customers and meet their needs appropriately and according to his preferences.

The increasing number of new products with various innovations shows how businesses are encouraged to stay competitive with the development of faster marketing strategies. This increasingly competitive business world serves a number of sectors and businesses that are already operating on a global scale. However, the state of a country including demographic growth rates, has an impact on the activities carried out by businesses. The level of community needs, including transportation, is influenced by the demographic growth rate that is still increasing. The continuity of human interaction and the ability to move goods from one location to another are both facilitated by transportation which also plays a role in human life. The presence of these public activities requires appropriate supporting facilities or infrastructure. Social activity is a feature of human existence as a collection of individuals.

Network or transportation services are included in supporting installations (Fatima & Moridpour, 2019). The community carries out various activities, and to carry out these activities the community needs transportation as a support or tool. As a result, transportation service providers compete with each other to attract customers by improving the quality of service and making it easier to order, more convenient to travel, more on time, etc.

Technology is now developing rapidly. Over time, the development of technology has become more and more significant because it allows people to carry out various activities more easily. Society can easily receive and transmit any kind of information from anywhere and anytime with the help of the internet, making it a technology that has developed into a trend. The profitable activities of some businesses can also be supported through the internet. Business people combine the internet with transportation, or what is often referred to as online transportation, when business people observe very promising profitable opportunities. Online transportation service is known for its accessibility, transparency, and tariff affordability. These points make online transportation have advantages over the existing conventional transportation service. As we know that it is an example of disruptive technology that makes customers have better bargaining position than the companies (Alamsyah & Rachmadiansyah, 2018). One of the companies that offers this online transportation service is Grab. Grab is one of the most popular online transportation in Indonesia, especially in Medan city. Grab is a transportation service company that provides mobile-based services in its operations to improve the ease of access for its customers and the welfare of workers in various informal sectors in Indonesia (Septiani et al., 2017). Nowadays there are company except Grab, so they competed to reach many customer by many strategies they were done. In this case related with the satisfaction of customer. Thus the company needs to assess what factors will affect customer satisfaction and how to meet customer expectations so that customers not easy to switch to competitors or in other words Loyalty customers will be created when customers feel satisfaction in receive the benefits of the company's services (Surya, 2019). Service quality encourages customers to establish a close relationship with the company so that it is the possible company to carefully understand its expectations and needs. Finally, customer satisfaction can create health in the company. Service quality is influenced by two variables, namely the service variable perceived service and expected service variables (expected service). According to Cronin J. Joseph, Jr. Steven A. Taylor (1992:55) in (Firatmadi, 2017) stated that Customer satisfaction will have a significant impact on repurchase . If there is a gap between the two the customer will not buy the product again.

Measurement of service quality is very important because satisfaction consumers are determined by many intangible factors. Not such as products that have a physical appearance that is easy to measure objectively. Management's failure to meet the expectations of consumers create a bad image for the company (Maulana, 2016). In conditions of very tight competition between companies, customer satisfaction is an important aspect to note to improve performance the company. In other words, the level of interest and customer expectations must be following the implementation or performance carried out by company. Companies must always pay attention to the things that considered important by customers to achieve their satisfaction (Firatmadi, 2017). So that the company also pay attention about

customer experience through customer satisfaction. Positive customer experience can be interpreted as satisfaction with experience formed through several successful experiences in choosing the online transportation. This experience causes consumers not to want to switch to other online transportation and ultimately creates customer satisfaction (McLean & Wilson, 2019). There are many research results that provide information that customer experience has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The better the customer experience will have an impact on higher customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, so providing a positive customer experience is an absolute thing that online transportation company must do (Pekovic & Rolland, 2020; Tyrväinen, Karjaluoto, & Saarijärvi, 2020; Japutra et al., 2020) in (Zaid & PATWAYATI, 2021).

Problem formulation

The following problem formulations have been identified based on the back-plan of the problem described:

1. The presence of competitors in online transportation makes grab not always the most frequently used online transportation.
2. Because the vehicles used by Grab drivers are inconvenient, customers believe that the quality of services provided by Grab is not always good.
3. Customers believe that Grab's services are not always of high quality as its drivers often fail to pick up and drop off passengers. Customers have a bad experience because the driver is unfriendly and disrespectful to customers.
4. Customers do not always use Grab as a means of daily transportation.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Based on how the problems raised above, here are the research objectives of the research:

To find out more about how service quality affects customer satisfaction with Grab users at the Faculty of Economics Stambuk 2017, Medan State University.

1. To find out more about the impact of customer experience on customer satisfaction for Grab users at the Faculty of Economics Stambuk 2017, Medan State University.
2. To learn more about the impact of customer satisfaction and service quality on Grab users, see Stambuk Faculty of Economics 2017, Medan State University.

Benefits of research

The following are the benefits of the research described in this study:

1. For researchers

To put into practice all the theories learned during the course and to expand the researcher's knowledge and understanding of the field of marketing management, specifically with regard to the quality of customer service, customer experience, and customer satisfaction.

2. For drivers

This research should be a source of knowledge to help achieve the goals that have been set and developed into a plan to increase productivity in the workplace by leveraging Grab's high level of customer service.

3. For Medan State University

Adding to the literature at Medan State University in the field of marketing management, focusing on how customer satisfaction is affected by the quality of service and experience.

4. For other researchers

The findings of this study can be used as a resource for future research in the same field.

The Relationship between Research Concepts and Hypothesis

Before testing hypotheses, researchers should spend more time forming concepts, developing valid measures, establishing the causal relationships between concepts and the functional form of those relationships, and identifying boundary conditions and auxiliary assumptions. Providing these inputs should be recognized and incentivized as a crucial goal in itself (Scheel et al., 2021). In this article, we discuss how the role of service quality and customer experience can affect the satisfaction of customers. So, research have some hypothesis to show later the significance of effect from service quality and customer experience through satisfaction of customers. Before hypothesis testing, researcher need concept by literature review of service quality and customer experience through satisfaction of customers. In addition, there are some previous research about the effect of service quality and customer experience on customer satisfaction, to relate this study with theory that relevance. In this study, there are free variable (X), that are service quality(X1) and customer experience(X2), then bound variable (Y) that is satisfaction customer. There two hypothesis as follows:

1) Service Quality (X1)

Hypothesis:

H_o : there is no a significant effect of service quality on customer satisfaction

H_a : there is a significant effect of service quality on customer satisfaction

1) Customer Experience (X2)

Hypothesis:

H_o : there is no a significant effect of customer experience on customer satisfaction

H_a : there is a significant effect of customer experience on customer satisfaction

The Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

Service quality refers to a level of the highest value and also the control of that highest value in order to meet customer needs (Tjiptono & Chandra, 2016: 59). In addition, based on the opinion expressed by Lewis & Boom summarized by Tjiptono & Chandra (2016: 125) defines service quality as a measure of the goodness of a service provided to be able to meet the expectations of customers who use it. According to research by Ecy Trisnawati, Setiawan

Assegaff, and Eni Rohaini (Trisnawati et al., 2019), there is a relationship between slow satisfaction and service quality. In addition, Yosamanta Vistara researcher Petrus T. Resi (Trisnawati et al., 2019) found a relationship between customer satisfaction and service quality. The author comes to the conclusion that service quality has an impact on customer satisfaction based on previous theories, opinions, and research that can be used as a basis.

The Effect of Customer Experience on Customer Satisfaction

According to (Ahmad & Ingle, 2011), the success of the company is influenced by the customer's interest in goods, services, or the company itself, as well as by authentic experiences that foster personal value. In this situation, customer experience is becoming increasingly important in marketing research as it affects how customers are trained in direct competition. Customer experience has a different definition of quality-of-service because it requires certain actions. Ikhsan Nurahman (2021) stated in a study that there is a relationship between slow experience and customer satisfaction (Nurahman, 2021). In addition, a study by Kevin Kalangie, Sifrid Pangemanan, and Merinda Pandowo (2018) found a link between happiness and the experiences of needs (Pardede et al., 2018). During this time, according to Kenny Febrina Salim and Catherine; Research by Dr. Fransisca Andreani, M.M. (2015), there is a relationship between customer happiness and experience. The author came to the conclusion that customer experience has an impact on customer satisfaction based on previous theories, opinions, and research on the subject (Salim et al., 2015).

The Effect of Service Quality and Customer Experience on Customer Satisfaction

According to Cashmere (2017: 64), customer happiness is directly influenced by the organization's ability to provide services that meet the customer's integrity and desires (Ahmad & Ingle, 2011). Irawan (2006:325) claims that managing the customer experience with a product or service is done through methodology, strategy, and implementation of enterprise customer management. Based on the theories, opinions and research discussed above, the author came to the conclusion that customer happiness is influenced by the quality of service and the client experience (Irawan, 2020).

3. RESEARCH METHODS

Population

According to Sugiyono (2012: 80), the concept of population has been introduced as a generalization zone consisting of items or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by the researcher to be studied and then drawn conclusions. The population includes not only humans but also other natural objects. The population of an object or subject includes all its characteristics and traits as a whole, not just the number of individuals who form that object or subject. A researcher must first clearly define the population that is the focus of their investigation, as well as the target population, or the group that will eventually form the perimeter of their findings. As a result, the conclusions are based on a research result, and in accordance with the principles of research ethics, these conclusions apply only to the selected demographic as the target audience. The aforementioned article is one of the sources of writing

to find out the population. Students of the Faculty of Economics, Medan Stambuk State University 2017 were the population used in this study.

Table 3.1: Recapitulation of the Number of Students of the Faculty of Economics Stambuk 2017

No	Department / Study Program	Sum
1	Economic Education	133
2	Accounting Education	113
3	Business Education	104
4	Office Administration Education	111
5	Accountancy	145
6	Management	144
	Total	750

Source: TU Academic Section Room

3.2.2 Samples

Sugiyono (2012) states that the size and characteristics of populace are part of the charm. Therefore, a sample is a segment of the population whose characteristics will be studied and can represent the entire population in order to have fewer yes than the population. The Slovin formula was used to calculate the number of pre-emergence samples as respondents in the study. These are as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N.e^2}$$

Information:

n = Number of samples

N = Total population

e = Percent of inaccuracy due to sampling errors that are still tolerable or desirable (e.g., 1%, 5%, 10%).

The number of students in this study at the Faculty of Economics Stambuk 2017 Medan State University was 750 people. Due to the large population, the Slovin formula will be applied, which is as follows with an error tolerance limit of 10%:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N.e^2}$$

$$n = \frac{750}{1+750.0,1^2}$$

$$n = \frac{750}{1+750.0,01}$$

$$n = \frac{750}{8,5}$$

$$n = 88.23$$

Based on the Slovin calculation above, the number of samples used in this study increased to 88.23 and adjusted to 90 respondents using the 10 % error type (0.1). The sample technique

used is non-probability sampling, that is, it does not provide an equal opportunity for each component or member of the population to be selected as a sample (Sugiyono, 2018: 82).

DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

4.3.1 Test Classical Assumptions

The goal of the classical assumption test is to find a problem with multiple linear regression models. The multiple linear regression model can be considered a good model if it supports the normality hypothesis and rejects the traditional statistical hypothesis of multicollinearity and heteroskedasticity.

4.5.1.1 Normality Test

The purpose of the normality test is to find out whether the model in the regression of dependent and independent variables has a normal distribution or not. A normal or close to normal data distribution is necessary for a good regression model.

Using the normal distribution of data in this regression model, it can also be determined from the P-Plot graph, which indicates that the data distribution is normal if the points around the diagonal line move in the same direction.

Figure 4.1: P-Plot Chart

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results (2022)

Based on the above graph, it is possible to see how the data is distributed in theseki tar and in the direction of the diagonal line. Although the data slows down somewhat and then follows the diagonal line again, it is still considered close to the normal distribution and according to demand, the data is evenly distributed.

Figure 4.2: Normality Test of Histogram Method

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results (2022)

Based on the figure above, it can be seen that the histogram line does not move to the right or to the left where it appears as a cloche pattern, indicating that the distribution of data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

To ensure whether there is a correlation between one free variable and another, use a multicollinearity test. If multicollinearity is found, the coefficient of the variable is unknown and the error becomes infinite. The diagnostic process for some collinearities involves the evaluation of the value of the tonary factor and the inflation variance (VIF). Multicollinearity testing is based on the premise that if the tolerance value is greater than 0.1 and the VIF value is less than 10, then there is no evidence of multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

Table 4.13: Data Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a							
Type	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIFs
(Constant)	1,406	,958		1,467	,146		
X1 Service Quality	,197	,080	,252	2,454	,016	,134	7,475
X2 Customer Experience	,548	,081	,698	6,803	,000	,134	7,475

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results (2022)

Based on the calculations in the table above, each independent variable has a tolerance value greater than 0.1 and a VIF value of less than 10. This shows that there is no multicollinearity between variables because the tolerance values for the Customer Experience (X2) and Service Quality (X1) variables are both 0.134. As a result, the VIF values for the customer experience measurement variables (X2) and quality of service (X1) were 7,475 each.

Heteroskedasticity Test

The classical assumption test in the regression model includes the heteroskedasticity test. There must be no evidence of heteroskedasticity for the regression model to be valid. If there are signs of heteroskedasticity, there will be uncertainty or inaccuracy in the results of analysis of the regression performed. Heteroskedasticity can be determined by looking at graphs in numerical form, including the prediction of variables independent with residual values. The methodologies used to calculate heteroskedasticity include:

- If there is a certain pattern, such as dots that form an irregular pattern (undulated, enlarged, and retracted), then heteroskedasticity has occurred.
- There is no heteroskedasticity if the points are distributed above and below the number 0 on the Y axis and there is no clear model.

Figure 4.3: Test Heteroskedasticity Using Scatterplot

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results (2022)

In the cloud point image above, it can be seen that the tick points are evenly distributed at point 0. Therefore, the data are free of heteroskedasticity and in line with research expectations, i.e., free from heteroskedasticity, allowing regression models to be used to predict the impact of Service Quality and Customer Experience on Subscriber P Satisfaction.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis seeks to ascertain whether or not a free variable (X) has an effect on a bound variable (Y). Models of multiple linear regression equations are used to explain the relationship between bound bell variables and free variables. To find out the relationship between customer satisfaction (Y) as a bound variable and service quality (X1) as a free variable, a linear equation model of multiple regression is used as follows:

Table 4.14: Multiple Regression Test

Type	Coefficients ^a				T	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	1,406	,958		1,467	,146	
X1 Service Quality	,197	,080	,252	2,454	,016	
X2 Customer Experience	,548	,081	,698	6,803	,000	

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Y Kepuasan

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results (2022)

Based on the table above, you can find out the constant value of 1.406, the service quality value of 0.197, and the customer experience value of 0.548. As a result, here is how the equation of a multiple regression model can be obtained:

$$Y = 1.406 + 197 X1 + 548 X2 + e$$

The regression equation above can be explained as follows:

- Obtained the value of the constant 1.406 indicates that assuming other factors are constant, the value of Y is 1.406 if the values of the free variables X1 and X2 are equal to zero.
- The service quality coefficient (X1) in the calculation of linear regression berganda is calculated at 0.197. This means that if X1 increases by 1% then the satisfaction of the n (Y) multiplier will increase by 0.197% assuming all other factors remain.
- The customer experience coefficient (X2) obtained from the calculation of multiple linear regression has a value of 0.548. That is, assuming that all other factors remain constant, if ada an increase of X2, the satisfaction of the offender n (Y) will increase by 0.548.

Hypothesis Test

T-test (Partial)

To ascertain whether the free variable (X) has a partial effect on the bound variable, a t (partial) (Y) test is performed. From the calculated value of t, this can be seen. A significant influence between an independent variable and a dependent variable occurs if the significance value tih is small or equal to 0.05. The opposite is true if the significance value of t is greater than or equal to 0.05.

Table 4.15: t-test (Partial)

Coefficients ^a					
Type	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1,406	,958		1,467	,146
X1_Service Quality	,197	,080	,252	2,454	,016
X2_Customer Experience	,548	,081	,698	6,803	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Y_Kepuasan

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results (2022)

The t-test table above shows that the following explanations can be used to explain the significance of each variable in this study:

1. Based on the hasil calculation of SPSS, the calculated t value for service quality (X1) is 2.454 and the t magnitude of the table with the provision of a significant level of 5 percent and the degree of freedom (dk) with the provision $dk = n - 2 - 1$ or $90 - 2 - 1 = 87$ and under this provision the t value of the table is 1.663. In this case, customer satisfaction is positively influenced by service quality which is indicated by a calculated t value $>$ a table t value of $2.454 > 1.663$ and a significance level of $0.016 > 0.05$. This shows that customer satisfaction is affected by service quality both partially and significantly, then H_0 is rejected while H_a is accepted.
2. Based on the results of the SPSS calculation, the t-statistical value for customer experience (X2) is 6,803 and the number of tables with a significant degree of 5% and the degree of freedom (et al) with a disposition of $dk = n - 2 - 1$ or $90 - 2 - 1 = 87$ and based on the disposition in i, the table value is 1.663. In this case, Customer Experience has a positive effect on customer satisfaction with a table t calculated $>$ t value of $6.803 > 1.663$ and a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that Customer Experience has a partial and significant effect on customer satisfaction, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

Test F (Simultaneous)

The F test (simultaneous) mainly shows if the independent variables included in the model have a combined effect on the dependent variables. A table of F test results is available for review below.

Table: Test F (Simultaneous)

ANOVA ^a						
Type		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6692,524	2	3346,262	311,571	,000 ^b
	Residual	934,376	87	10,740		
	Total	7626,900	89			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Y_Kepuasan						
b. Predictors: (Constant), X2_Customer Experience, X1_Service Quality						

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results (2022)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the value of F is 311.571, the value of the table F with a significant degree of 5%, and the degree of error (et al) a is $90 - 2 - 1 = 87$. (3 100). H_0 is rejected; H_a is accepted if F counts $> F$ table $311,571 > 3,100$. We can emphasize that service quality and customer experience together have a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction.

Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) aims to find out the percentage of influence exerted by the variable X which simultaneously affects the variable Y. R Square is used as the value of R^2 in statistical calculations. Here is a list of the results of the determination test:

Table: Coefficient of Determination Test

Model Summary ^b				
Type	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,937 ^a	,877	,875	3,277
a. Predictors: (Constant), X2_Customer Experience, X1_Service Quality				
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Y_Kepuasan				

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results (2022)

Based on the table above, the coefficient of determination of R Square is 0.877. According to the value of R Square, an independent variable can explain 87.7% of its effect on the variable dependent. The variables of service quality and customer experience can both be used to explain how the effect is limited to the variables of Customer Satisfaction. The rest ($100\% - 87.7\% = 12.3\%$) is influenced by other factors that are outside the variables studied.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Following the results of the exposition and debate in the previous chapter, here are the findings of this study:

1. Based on partial research, the variable service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction in Grab transportation users. This is indicated by a calculated t value of 2.454 and a table t value of 1.663 with a significance level of 0.00

- because $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($2.454 > 1.663$), the significance is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), and the regression coefficient is positive with a value of 0.197.
2. Based on the results of partial research, variable customer experience has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction there are Grab transportation users. This is evidenced by a calculated t value of 6.803 and a t_{table} of 1.663 with a significant degree of $sig < 0.05$ because $t_{hitung} > t_{table}$ ($6.803 > 1.663$), its significance is more small than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), and the regression coefficient is positive with a value of 0.549.
 3. Based on the results of the study, the calculated F value of $311,571 > 1,663$ showed positive results. Therefore, the values obtained on the sig column $0.000 < 0.05$ are significant. Thus, it can be said that service quality and customer experience, both separately and together, have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction among Grab transportation users.
 4. Based on the results of the calculation of the coefficient of determination, it can be known that the value of R^2 obtained is 0.877. This figure shows that 87.7% of service quality and customer experience (bound variables) can be well explained. The remaining 12.3% was influenced by additional factors not included in the study.

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